

POLYMER AND COMPOSITE IN THE AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY EFFICIENCY OF USING MATERIALS INDICATORS

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Usmanov Ilhomjon Ikromjanovich

Tashkent State Transport University

Assistant of the Department of Transport Power Equipment

Annotation: *Fuel consumption of the car and thus the amount of toxic gases one of the main ways to reduce this is to reduce the weight of the cars. Polymer and composite materials in the weight reduction of cars in use. Polymer and composite materials are stronger than steel, is a material that reduces the environmental risk of cars and automobiles. Application of polymer and composite materials in the automotive industry reducing the weight of cars and increasing fuel economy durable, resistant to corrosion, corrosion, temperature and other adverse effects of the environment resistant to the negative effects of the car on the environment, ie noise and material with low emission properties, quenching vibrations*

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We live in a time when science is advancing rapidly. New inventions, innovations and developments are being created in all spheres of our life. But some aspects of the devices and techniques we use have hardly changed since they appeared. Let's take the most obvious example of a technology that has changed our lives in the last century: it's a car. In many ways, today's cars have radically changed in appearance and design than the first cars created, but the materials used to assemble them have hardly changed. In other words, 99.9% of all cars on the road are made of steel. This makes the car heavier, resulting in increased fuel consumption, which in turn increases the amount of toxic gases and noise (engine noise) released into the environment, which is the most pressing environmental problem today. .

The main and long-term trend of the global automotive industry is to reduce the harmful effects of these vehicles on the environment and increase fuel efficiency. One of the main ways to reduce fuel consumption and thus the

amount of toxic gases is to reduce the weight of these cars. It is known from car theory that every 10% reduction in car weight leads to a 5-7% increase in fuel economy. Reducing car mass is not only a major goal for the automotive industry but also necessary for the global environmental safety.

In addition to aluminum, polymeric materials are used to reduce the weight of cars. Polymeric materials are also used in electric cars, which are considered to be a new generation of cars, further improving them and increasing their performance. Replacing heavy materials such as metal and glass in car parts with polymer material reduces vehicle weight, eliminates noise, and further increases energy savings. In addition to other advantages of polymers, thermoplastic and polyolefin polymers are safer and lighter than steel bumpers, while polycarbonate is better, stronger and more modern than glass headlights.

Currently, polymer materials account for 1/3 of the nearly 30,000 parts in a vehicle. In total, about 39 different types of basic polymers are used in automobile production. More than 70% of the polymers used in automobiles are composed of four polymers: polypropylene, polyurethane, polyamides, and polyvinyl chloride. Polymer and composite materials allow the vehicle to meet high safety standards, the use of such materials in the automotive industry allows minimizing the mass of parts used in vehicles and makes it easier to work on the design than metals.

Over the years

Picture 1. Distribution of polymer and composite materials in cars by years.

The amount of polymer and composite materials used in automobiles is increasing over time (Picture 1). In 1960, North American cars contained an average of 8 kg of polymer and composite materials. In 2016, the car was made

of 151 kg of polymer and composite materials. This is about 8 percent of the car's weight and 50 percent of the materials in the car.

The use of polymer and composite materials saves automakers money due to its low cost, ensuring that the car interior is sleek and noise-free. At the same time, composite materials have great advantages over steel in the automotive industry, such as polymers, which means that composite materials are lighter, safer and more durable. The use of polymer and composite materials in automobiles is fully compliant with fuel economy standards, and more polymer and composite materials are needed to reduce weight. In automobiles, steel and aluminum materials were mainly used in load-bearing elements, body parts, transmission and friction parts, heat exchangers, and parts operating at high temperatures. The emergence and improvement of carbon fiber composite materials in the automotive industry, which are resistant to corrosion, moisture and various temperatures, has allowed cars to run more lightly and efficiently.

The capabilities of composite materials meet the basic requirements of the automotive industry and provide the following effective operational characteristics:

- Low coefficient of expansion for thermal conductivity;
- Excellent dimensional stability for shape retention and reliability;
- Corrosion resistance for operation in wet and dry conditions;
- Relatively low weight to reduce overall vehicle mass;
- Noise suppression;
- Ability to accept dyes and quality acceptance of dye;
- Relatively low cost, ease of production.

Composite materials are used in the following parts of the car:

- Air deflectors and spoilers (air dams);
- In collectors; In battery housings and covers;
- On bumpers and bumper handles;
- On engine heads and covers;
- In car door and window frames;
- In the control panel;
- Headlights;
- In heat and noise protection coatings;
- In the car body.

By using polymers in the automotive industry, we achieve the following efficiency:

- ✓ the appearance of the car is improved;
- ✓ its mass decreases;
- ✓ noise is reduced;
- ✓ improve the design of details;
- ✓ the service life of spare parts is extended;
- ✓ Technological processes in production have been simplified.

In the production of complex, light, high-quality and durable parts of cars, the replacement of metals with plastics provides significant technical and economic benefits, as polymer and composite materials meet these requirements, low cost of production, minimal waste as a result of recycling and as a result will remain a major raw material for the automotive industry now and in the future, with qualities such as a positive impact on emissions reduction, traffic noise suppression and long-term use.

The use of polymer and composite materials in the automotive industry increases the fuel economy by reducing the weight of cars, while this low-cost material is durable, resistant to corrosion, corrosion, temperature and other environmental influences, and the car is environmentally friendly. is a material with low emission properties, ie noise and vibration suppression. The use of polymer and composite materials in the automotive industry of the country, in the automotive industry, the production of high-quality, competitive, fuel-efficient, environmentally friendly and affordable for consumers is highly effective and meets all the requirements. responds.

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